

Paper 9

Green Marketing –Consumer’s Perception And Awareness Towards Green Products, A Study Of Mangalore City

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Abstract

Concerns have been expressed by manufacturers and customers about the environmental impact of products during recent decades. Consumers and manufacturers have directed their attention toward environment friendly products that are presumed to be “green” or environment friendly like low power consuming (energy-efficient) electrical appliances, organic foods, lead free paints, recyclable paper. Indian marketers are also realizing the importance of the Green Marketing Concept. Although a variety of research on green marketing has been conducted across the country; little academic research on consumer perception and preferences has been carried out. There has been a change in consumer attitudes towards a green lifestyle. People are actively trying to reduce their impact on the environment. However, this is not widespread and is still evolving. Organizations and business however have seen this change in consumer attitudes and are trying to gain an edge in the competitive market by exploiting the potential in the green market industry. The current study introduces the concept of green marketing and looks into the various ways in which the different consumer attributes are related to the concept of green marketing. This paper highlights the consumers ‘perception and preferences towards green marketing practices and products with the help of structured questionnaire. Research has given good insights for marketers of the green products and suggests the need of designing the marketing communication campaigns promoting green products due to high green value among the consumers.

Introduction

Today the concept of sustainability is almost ubiquitous by showing application in corporate strategy, consumer choice, student education and academic research. The need for sustainable business practices by corporations around the world is identified to be a result of overall increase in the consumer awareness of lack of environmental protection and social inequities. Over the last decade environmentalism has emerged to be a vital aspect due to increasing issues related to acid rains, depletion of the ozone layer, and degradation of the land and many more pressing environmental issues. This resulted in increase in consumer concern with regards to restoration of ecological balance by presenting demands for eco friendly products in countries around the world (Doyle 1992; Vandermerwe and Oliff 1990). The research on

environmental consumerism is a well researched topic with the first research dating back to the 1970s (Henion and Kinnear, 1976). There has been extensive growth in interest exhibited by marketing academics as well as practitioners with regard to the impact of marketing on promoting and maintaining ecological balance (Chammaro et al., 2009; Bhattacharya, 2011). There is a great deal of depletion of non-renewable energy resources which accompanied by generation of non-bio degradable pollutants has led to an increase in consumer and corporate awareness of green marketing issues. The growth of green marketing research dates back to 1980s when there was emergence of concept of green marketing. Early literature indicates green marketing to be an approach which indicated signs of shift in consumer attention to green product. At that time green marketing research concentrated on the shift in consumer consumption of green products. There was a great deal of empirical research carried out to identify interest among consumers in using and purchasing green products (Mintel 1991). Green marketing approach was researched from a corporate interest point of view in the early 90s. Research indicated that 92% of MNCs from Europe changed their products to address growing concerns of environmental pollution. (Vandermerwe and Oliff, 1990). Green marketing research has come a long way since then. Consumers from the developed countries including USA and Western Europe were found to be more conscious about the environment (Curlo, 1999). Research in the last decade (Lee, 2009, Rahbar and Wahid, 2011, Lee 2008; D Souza 2004) has indicated that consumer are aware and are willing to pay more to "go green". There is limited research which has examined the impact of green marketing on consumers from emerging economies like India (Bhattacharya, 2011; Prakash, 2002). Most of the studies related to green consumerism have been conducted in well developed countries. It is to be acknowledged that when considered from a developing country context there is a lack in number of studies. It is against this backdrop from the above discussion it is quite clear that there is a large research gap in terms conceptually identifying those areas of consumer awareness impacting the concept of green marketing.

Literature review

A topic that the media, politicians, organisations and general public have been talking about during the past decade is the environmental friendliness or so called "green marketing". Consumers began to espouse concern for the environment. In fact, through a survey carried out in America, Gutfield (1991) found that eight out of ten consumers were claiming to be environmentalists (cited in Grove, Fisk, Pickett & Kangun, 1996). According to Mainieri and Barnett, 1997, as cited in Juwaheer, 2005, the environment has faced massive destructive changes: diminution of natural resources, damage to the ozone layer, and loss of agricultural land. In the recent years, due to the massive amount of environmental pollution caused by firms in the world, people have become more aware of the environmental issues. Therefore, due to the attention of the society, many organisations have started to accept their environmental responsibility (Chen, 2010). Similarly, Kangun et al., 1991 as cited in Martin & Simintiras, 1995 argued that firms were trying to respond to the rising environmental

concern of consumers by selling green products. Consequently, many organisations started to promote themselves as green companies, that is, they began to produce and market goods or services in a way which minimises damage to the environment. Customers often link green marketing with terms such as recyclable, refillable, ozone friendly and environmentally friendly (Polonsky, 1994 and Li, 2008). Whilst these terms are green marketing claims, in general, green marketing is a much broader concept. Green marketing is applicable to consumer goods, industrial goods and as well as services. Theoretically speaking, green marketing is about designing, developing and delivering products that are eco friendly which cause less as possible harm to the environment and its stakeholders.

Later, Polonsky (1994) proposed a definition of green marketing which has a broader focus than those of other investigators and it also includes all main elements of other definitions. His definition is as follows:

"Green or Environmental Marketing consists of all activities designed to generate and facilitate any exchanges intended to satisfy human needs or wants, such that the satisfaction of these needs and wants occurs, with minimal detrimental impact on the natural environment"

This definition embraces all the conventional components of the marketing definition that is "all activities designed to generate and facilitate any exchanges intended to satisfy human needs or wants" (Stanton & Futrell 1987, as cited in Polonsky, 1994). It also makes sure that the interests of both the organisation and the customers are protected, that is, there will be no exchange until both the buyer and seller benefit mutually. Moreover, this definition incorporates the protection of the natural environment, by trying to lessen the negative impact that the exchange can have on the natural environment.

. As customers were buying products and services that were less detrimental to the natural environment, organisations were forced to change their selling behaviours (Ottman, 1992; Peattie, 1992, 1995; Vandermerwe & Oliff, 1990, as cited in Chen, 2010).

Moloy Ghoshal (2011) examined that green marketing was still in infancy. In the perception of marketing scholars, green marketing refers to eco-level and market segmentation and the role of structural factors and economic incentives in influencing consumer behavior. The green marketers must understand to satisfy two objectives: improved environmental quality and customer satisfaction.

K.K.Shrivastava & Sujata Khandai, the author of *Consumer Behaviour in Indian Context*, has discussed green marketing legislation in association with the multinational corporations. These face a growing variety of legislation designed to address environmental issues. Global concern for the environment extends beyond industrial pollution, hazardous waste disposal and rampant deforestation to include issues that focus directly on consumer products. Cateora Graham, in *International Marketing*, has drawn a parallel line between green marketing and product development. The author has cited a variety of examples where the importance of

green marketing has been laid focus on. Green marketing is term used to identify concern with the environmental consequences of a variety of marketing activities. It very evident from the author's research and examples the packaging and solid waste rules are burdensome but there are successful cases of not only meeting local standards but also being able to transfer this approach to other markets.

Ginsberg, J.M. & Bloom, P.N. (2004). Choosing the Right Green-Marketing Strategy. MIT Sloan Management Review, 46(1), pp. 79-88.

Green marketing has not lived up to the hopes and dreams of many managers and activists. Although public opinion polls consistently show that consumers would prefer to choose a green product over one that is less friendly to the environment when all other things are equal, those "other things" are rarely equal in the minds of consumers. How then, should companies handle the dilemmas associated with green marketing? They must always keep in mind that consumers are unlikely to compromise on traditional product attributes, such as convenience, availability, price, quality and performance. It's even more important to realize, however, that there is no single green-marketing strategy that is right for every company. It is suggested that companies should follow one of four strategies, depending on market and competitive conditions, from the relatively passive and silent "lean green" approach to the more aggressive and visible "extreme green" approach - with "defensive green" and "shaded green" in between. Managers who understand these strategies and the underlying reasoning behind them will be better prepared to help their companies benefit from an environmentally friendly approach to marketing.

Research methodology

Researcher have used structured questionnaire. Primary data was collected from respondents of Mangalore city through a questionnaire designed for a sample of 85 respondents .

Random sampling method was adopted by the researcher and selected the samples from Mangalore region representing both the genders, different age groups, education level, marital status and monthly income. The data collected from the respondents are coded, tabulated and analysed into logical statements.

Secondary data was collected from the available literature, journals and web search wherever necessary. The Questionnaire method was chosen for its versatility speed and cost benefits.

The study has been carried out keeping in mind the following primary **objectives**:

- To understand the awareness of consumers towards green marketing.
- To assess the attitude of consumers towards green branding.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table and Graph 1. Occupation of the respondents

Response	No of Respondents	Percentage
Employee	33	39%
Entrepreneur	02	02%
Student	50	59%
Total	85	100%

The majority of the respondents are students and as many as 39% of the respondents are employees

Table and Graph 2 shows belief in the concept of green marketing

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	81	95%
No	00	00%
Cant say	04	05%
Total	85	100%

As many as 95% Of the respondents believe in the concepts of green marketing

Table and Graph 3. Awareness regarding of the fact that the companies are going green

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	72	84%
No	14	16%
Total	85	100%

Public awareness exists regarding the changes that are taking place from traditional marketing to green marketing

Table and Graph 4 Sources of awareness of Green products or ‘Eco Friendly products’

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Television	09	11%
Magazine	00	00%
Class lecture	41	48%
Newspaper	16	19%
Other	19	22%
Total	85	100%

Many of the respondents have got information about green marketing through class lectures. Television is also one of the major source of information

Table and Graph 5: traditional marketing techniques harm the environment

Response	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	48	56%
No	13	15%
Depends	24	28%
Total	85	100%

Table and Graph 6: the Productivity can be improved drastically by using green marketing

Response	No of Respondents	Percentages
Yes	15	18%
No	07	08%
Cant say	63	74%
Total	85	100%

Table and Graph 7: Government should take initiative in making companies to go green

Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	85	100%
No	00	00%
Don't know	00	00%
Total	85	100%

Table and Graph 8: willingness to pay more for the green products

Response	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	45	53%
No	06	7%
Cant say	34	40%
Total	85	100%

Findings

Majority of the respondents are both aware of the concept of green marketing and do believe in green marketing. And major source of information is the class lecture and also television. This is may be because of the fact that as many as 50 respondents out of 85 are students. And it is clear from the study that majority of the respondents are aware of the uses of green marketing in protecting and preserving the environment Consumers have expressed **strong concerns** about the concept of green marketing and companies going green. Apart from this, consumers are well aware of the fact that the productivity of companies can be drastically improved.

People are aware of green environment because it is less detrimental to the environment and companies can look into implementation of this concept for betterment of business. As far as initiation of green marketing is concerned everyone are responsible for green marketing. If we analyze the facts pertaining to green marketing the significant results are positive at one end. On other end, consumers say that it is difficult for all the companies to implement green marketing. Environmental education refers to organized efforts to teach about how natural environments function and particularly how human beings can manage their behaviour and ecosystems in order to live sustainable

Recommendations and Conclusion

Green marketing is a continuous process that requires constant inputs from the suppliers, government legislations and policies and the people. This is required so that the businesses green marketing strategy can be aligned to the target markets and so it can gain a sustainable competitive advantage. It is important that strategies and policies in relation to green products be developed and implemented so as to guide and help the retailers and customers towards a green change. Businesses should concentrate on focusing on developing a green product that have a demand from the general public and which also aligns to the company's core positioning. Furthermore businesses should also present efforts in a manner that reduces the risk related to costs. In conclusion, creating and implementing a green marketing strategy is not straight forward because it is not only complex, but also a relative concept that continuously varies over time. The framework that is presented in the current paper is based on the need to explain inconsistencies in attitudes and behaviors that have been revealed in past researches Thus the current study will also be of benefit to the green marketers as it aids in developing a marketing strategy that persuades consumers to seek the value of collective gain over self-interest.

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